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ABSTRACT BOOK

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A Research on Customer Behaviours Determination Concerning Bee Products in Southeast Anatolian Region

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Abstract

In this study, the bee products' recognition and the determination of consumption behaviors were aimed. The provinces were determined in the research first as the population numbers which represent the 7 geographical regions in Turkey were considered. Accordingly, Istanbul, Bursa, Izmir, Manisa, Ankara, Konya, Van, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Sanliurfa, Adana, Antalya, Samsun and Trabzon, which are the provinces, were chosen. The survey was made with 1.834 consumers in total in all the provinces as 234 participants from Gaziantep and Sanliurfa which represent Southern East Anatolia Region. The arithmetic and weighted means, the frequency tables were used with the main statistical transactions such as the ratio and percentage in the analysis evaluation of the data which was obtained from the households who participated into the survey.

90,58% of the participants in Southern East Anatolia Region stated that they consume the honey in their daily life but 9,41% of them stated that they don't consume the honey. 65,70% of the consumers consume the extracted honey, 15,00% of them consume the honey with comb, 19,30 of them consume both of them. 89,19% of the consumers consume the honey in the mornings, 1,08% of them consume the honey before the sleeping and 9,19% of them consume the honey more than one time in a day. 37,50 % of the consumers stated that they consume the honey everyday, 25% of them stated that they consume the honey once in a few days and 37,50% of them stated that they consume the honey sometimes. 50,00% of the consumers buy the honey from the bee breeders 43,05% of them buy the honey from the market and 6,95% of them buy the honey from the different places (such as the district bazaars, acquaintances). 48,81% of the consumers stated the factors to buy the honey with a brand as they think that it is more reliable than the others, 17,68% of them stated their reasons as they find it easily, 28,76 % of them stated their reasons as it has got a label with the explanatory information and 5,4,75% of them stated their reasons with the other factors. 51,09% of the consumers stated the factors to buy the honey without any brand as they think that it is more natural and reliable than the others, 20,65% % of them stated their reasons as they can find it easily, 25,18% of them stated their reasons as it is cheaper than the others and 3,08% of them stated their reasons with the other factors. When the consumers were asked about what the packing type is as their preference to buy the honey, 72,16% of them answered as the glass packing, 17,05% of them answered as the tin packing, 2,27% of them answered as the plastic packing and 8,52% of them answered as the other packings. 85,71% of the consumers stated that they prefer the flower honey, 2,20 % of them stated that they prefer the honeydew honey, 6,59% of them stated that they prefer the chestnut honey and 5,49% of them stated that they prefer the other monofloral honey (citrus, sunflower, acacia, lavender and cotton). 7,92% of the consumers stated that they consume one or a few of the other bee products except from the honey but 92,08% of them stated that they don't consume any bee products except from the honey..

In the study that the consumers' consumption habit for the bee products in Southern East Anatolia Region was reviewed, the recognition of the other bee products except from the honey and their lower consumption ratio rather than the other regions were revealed.

Key Words: Honey, Pollen, Royal jelly, Customer Behaviours